

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Platinum with Benzyldimethylphenylammonium Chloride

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A number of quaternary ammonium salts have been reported in the determination of metal ions in micro quantities in solution. Yoshimura and Ueno¹ used benzyldimethylphenylammonium (BDPA) chloride in the determination of Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Mo^V in SCN⁻ solution. It has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of bismuth² and palladium³. The present work describes a sensitive and selective method for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of platinum(IV) at trace level using BDPA chloride as reagent and 1,2-dichloroethane as extractant.

Results and Discussion

When potassium iodide solution is added to a slightly acidic solution containing micro amounts of platinum(IV), light pink hexaiodoplatinate(IV) ion is produced which is not extractable into 1,2-dichloroethane. BDPA chloride reacts with hexaiodoplatinate(IV) yielding the ion-pair [BDPA]₂-[PtI₆] in the form of a light pink precipitate which is completely extractable into 1,2-dichloroethane in presence of a little amount of dimethylformamide. The colour of the extract becomes yellow and exhibits maximum absorbance at 364 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.2–11.0 µg ml⁻¹ of platinum in the extract. The reagent blank shows some absorbance at 364 nm and hence all measurements are made against a reagent blank. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are 2.54

$\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.00764 \text{ } \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

The complex exhibits constant and maximum absorption provided the acidity of the aqueous phase is maintained at 1.5×10^{-4} to $6.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ with respect to HCl. In respect of potassium iodide concentration on the absorbance, it is found that the concentration below $7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and beyond $3.75 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ of it in the aqueous phase yields low values of absorbance. As regards the reagent concentration, 1 ml of 0.02 M BDPA chloride is adequate for the complete extraction of the complex for the given range of platinum concentration. Reagent concentration below $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and beyond $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ in the aqueous phase results in the decrease of absorbance value. For extraction of the complex in the solvent 1,2-dichloroethane, addition of a little amount of dimethylformamide is essential before addition of the solvent. It dissolves the ion-association complex precipitate forming a clear solution and also plays a significant role in increasing stability and colour intensity of the extracted species. The minimum amount of dimethylformamide required to dissolve completely the precipitate formed within the given range of platinum concentration, is 0.5 ml, and if the amount of added dimethylformamide exceeds 2 ml, the absorbance value shows a diminishing tendency. The absorbance value remains constant over a period of 12 h.

Various solvents such as chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, methyl isobutyl ketone, benzene, isoamyl alcohol and isobutanol were also tested for extraction of the complex, but 1,2-dichloroethane was found to be the most effective one, because the complex is not extractable into carbon tetrachloride and is partially extractable into isoamyl alcohol, benzene, isobutanol and 1-butanol. Though the complex is completely extractable into chloroform and isobutyl methyl ketone, the absorbance value does not remain constant. Hence, 1,2-dichloroethane is used as solvent. In combination with dimethylformamide, 10 ml of 1,2-dichloroethane extracts the complex completely by a single extraction.

The absorption spectra of the ion-association complex of platinum in 1,2-dichloroethane (3.7 µg ml⁻¹ of Pt) against the reagent blank show that absorbance due to reagent blank at 364 nm is negligible.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-3210 spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used.

A stock solution of platinum(IV) was prepared from H₂PtCl₆.6H₂O and standardised by known method⁴, and the test solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilution. The reagent BDPA chloride was prepared by mixing equal amounts of benzyl chloride and *N,N*-dimethylaniline at room temperature. A 0.02 M solution of BDPA chloride and a 0.3 M solution of KI were prepared in distilled water.

All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing 2–110 µg of platinum(IV) was made acidic with 0.00625 M HCl (1 ml), and to it KI solution (1 ml) and BDPA chloride (1 ml) were added. The total volume was made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The resulting mixture having been mixed with dimethylformamide (0.5 ml) and 1,2-dichloroethane (10 ml)

was shaken for 1 min and the organic layer was then separated. Absorbance of the extract was measured at 364 nm against the reagent blank. Amounts of platinum in unknown solution was calculated from the standard calibration curve.

Effect of diverse ions : To test the effect of foreign ions on the extraction behaviour, platinum(IV) was extracted and estimated according to the recommended procedure in presence of diverse ions. The tolerance limit was set at the amount required to cause less than 3% error in the recovery of platinum, but the upper concentration limit of the foreign ions investigated was restricted to 200-fold w/w ratio to platinum taken. The extraction acidity was set at around 6.25×10^{-4} M with respect to HCl. It is found that Pt (37 µg) could be determined without interference in presence of 200-fold excess of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II}; 50-fold excess of Cr^{III} and Fe^{II}. The tolerance limit for W^{VI}, V^V, Ir^{III}, Ag^I, Fe^{III}, Pb^{II}, Sb^{III} and Cd^{II} is low (0.06–1.30). Pd^{II} and Ru^{III} interfere seriously. Higher tolerance limits (7.7–10.0) have been found for EDTA, F⁻, oxalate and phosphate; for Br⁻

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF PLATINUM IN VARIOUS SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl no	Ions added (in µg)	Masking agent used* (in µg)	Pt found (µg)** (Average of 3 determinations)
1.	Co ^{II} (8 000), Mo ^{VI} (816) Fe ^{III} (851)	EDTA (10 000)	36.8
2.	Mn ^{II} (8 700), Zn ^{II} (900), Br ^{III} (240)	EDTA (10 000)	36.6
3.	Ru ^{III} (360), Ni ^{II} (9 600), V ^V (1 360)	Oxalate (9 500)	36.3
4.	Co ^{II} (8 000), Ni ^{II} (9 600), Ir ^{III} (644)	Tartrate (5 000)	37.4
5.	Cr ^{III} (1 000), Mn ^{II} (8 700), Pd ^{II} (105)	Pd ^{II} is removed by extraction with 0.1% DMG solution in IBMK	36.1
6.	Au ^{III} (244), Fe ^{II} (1 860), Mn ^{II} (8 700)	Bromide (4000)	37.1

*DMG = dimethylglyoxime, IBMK = isobutyl methyl ketone.
** Average of 3 determinations

and tartrate these are 4.0 and 5.2 respectively. Interference due to ruthenium can be removed by using oxalate as masking agent. Pd^{II} if present, requires prior removal by extracting with dimethylglyoxime in isobutyl methyl ketone.

Precision and accuracy : A standard solution containing 37 µg of platinum was estimated 20 times by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.48 with a standard deviation of 0.0073 absorbance unit and a coefficient of variation of 1.5%. The present method was found to be rapid and simple, and provided excellent recovery of platinum in micro quantities in presence of some of the common ions. The present method seems to be superior to most of the existing methods⁵. The method was tested on a number of synthetic mixtures and the results are shown in Table I.

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